

Grading and Sequencing Tasks in Task-Based Syllabus: A Critical Look at Criterion Selection

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Abstract : Abstract—The necessity of grading and sequencing tasks has led to the development of different criteria in this regard. However, appropriateness of these criteria in different situations is less discussed. This paper attempts to shed more light on the priority of different criteria in relation with different factors including learners, teachers, educational, and cultural factors.

Keywords : Criteria, Grading, Sequencing, Language learning tasks

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